

Digital Access and Layers of Digital Divide in India

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Abstract: The digital divide in India both in the access and usage of ICTs and the internet is real and deep. It leads to an exclusionary consequence in the education, health and finance sectors. In a country plagued by high socioeconomic inequality, the digitisation process will take time particularly considering the existing human Capital indicators. The digital divide becomes particularly problematic when half of the population neither has access to gadgets and the internet or the technological know-how to move to a digital environment. There is a dire requirement of increasing the adoption and usage of ICTs among the less-favorable demographic profile (older age groups and women) and social groups of digital divide.

Index terms: Accessibility, empowerment, digital competence, economic progress, communication, social divide, Human capital indicators

INTRODUCTION

Information technologies have brought fundamental changes throughout society, driving it forward from the industrial age to the networked era. The ICT revolution has radically improved connectivity across the globe, and has pervaded into several aspects of modern human life. The Internet has changed business, education, government, healthcare, and even the ways in which we interact with our loved ones—it has become one of the key drivers of social evolution. ICT networks and services have changed the way businesses improve, compete and increase productivity (Jovanovic and Rousseau, 2005; Liao, Wang, Li, and Weyman-Jones 2016). The ways to communicate, access information, transact, shop, voice opinion, avail consumer and government services have changed and enabled by the click of a button. ICT has also impacted the delivery of developmental services such as healthcare, financial services, e-commerce and education (Foster and Heeks, 2013; Srivastava and Shainesh, 2015; Leong, Pan, Sue, and Cui, 2016).

The United Nations (2015, 2016) also recognises ICT as an enabler to achieve the Millennium Development Goals and the Sustainable Development Goals. Scholarly evidence confirms that ICT facilitates poverty reduction, and

promotes economic growth and welfare (Hardy, 1980; Norton, 1992; Röller and Waverman, 2001; Jensen, 2007). Based on prior research, ICT has been regarded as the ‘Liberation Technology’; which impacts the growth of developing economies more as compared to that of the developed economies (Waverman, Meschi, and Fuss, 2005; Qiang, Rossotto and Kimura, 2009). A ten per cent rise in broadband penetration leads to 1.21 per cent improvement in per capita GDP of the developed countries and 1.38 per cent improvement in per capita GDP of developing countries (Qiang et al., 2009). In the case of emerging India, it is observed that a ten per cent rise in the telecommunications investment improves the state per capita GDP by over 3 per cent; while a ten per cent increase in the Internet subscriptions augments India’s state per capita GDP 3.2 per cent (ICRIER, 2018).

DEFINING DIGITAL DIVIDE

Given ICTs potential to improve economic growth and development, there could be equity repercussions if certain sections of the population are not included digitally. Several scholarly researches have indicated empirically that the existing socio-economic disparities associated with digital differences, further magnify/intensify if the existing digital divide is not bridged (Avgerou and Madon, 2005; Wei, Teo, Chan, and Tan, 2011). According to Van Dijk (1999) there are four types of impediments to digital inclusion: lack of - ‘material access’, ‘mental or educational access’, ‘skill access’, and ‘usage access’. Norris (2001) considers digital divide as a multidimensional phenomenon, and differentiates between the global digital divide (access to Internet), the social divide (information gap among nations) and the democratic divide (engagement in public life through digital resources). According to the World Information Society report (WIS, 2007) digital inequalities exist at several levels: among nations, among regions of the same country, within organizations, amongst men and women, between age groups, religions, etc. Several indices have been developed at the world level; some of these indices are: the UNDP’s Technology Achievement Index; ITU’s Digital Access Index; World Economic Forum’s Network Readiness Index; and ORBICOM’s Monitoring the Digital Divide (UNDP, 2001; ITU, 2003; World Economic Forum, 2002 and ORBICOM, 2004).

Given several researches and indices developed by credible organizations and academia, the previous understanding of the digital divide in terms of mere access to ICTs has undergone a change. The factors leading to the digital divide can be summarized as the gap between 1) older generation and the digital natives, 2) level of education, 3) gender inequality and 4) high income — low income groups. These factors are further influenced by the geographical location, Rural-urban divide, and Governmental policies. All these factors determine the level of skills of an individual and the quality of access of ICTs which determines their position in the digital divide.

INITIATIVES BY GOVERNMENT OF INDIA

The government of India is determined to reduce the digital divide among people, regions and sectors with regards to ICTs. Several initiatives have been taken since the year 2000 to achieve this aim. More recently, the Indian government launched the ‘Digital India’ initiative to improve online infrastructure and increase internet accessibility among citizens (for example, linking rural areas to high-speed internet networks); thereby, empowering the country

to become more digitally advanced. The initiative encompasses three key objectives: to establish a secure and stable digital infrastructure, to deliver digital services and to ensure that every citizen has access to the Internet. Several programmes were undertaken by the government to deliver citizen services digitally (education, health, finance, land records, justice, e-governance, etc.) under National eGovernance Plan (NeGP), National Mission in Education, National Mission for Delivery of Justice and Legal Reforms, m-Kisan, Social Endeavour for Health and Telemedicine (SEHAT) and National Agriculture Market (e-NAM). The e-governance plan covers 31 mission projects including domains such as agriculture, land records, health, education, passport, law and order, municipalities, commercial taxes, income tax, public distribution system, postal services and basic banking services.

India now accounts for a large pool of wireless communications subscribers and Internet users. However, there are significant differences in India’s ICT adoption and its usage. India’s overall tele-density is 85% with urban tele-density (approx. 135 per cent) close to three times of the rural tele-density (approx. 58 per cent), while about 70 per cent of India’s population resides in the rural sector (Census, 2011; TRAI 2022). The total internet users in India is approx 851 million but with a great urban rural divide. While usage in rural areas is only about 38 subscribers per 100 population, in urban areas, it is 105 subscribers per 100 population. The overall average of the country is 61.6 internet subscribers per 100 population but clearly the data is skewed particularly since a larger population lives in rural areas (TRAI, 2022). There are wide disparities across various states in the adoption of ICTs. Kerala service area has the highest Rural Tele-density of 215.31 followed by Himachal Pradesh service area of 97.33. Madhya Pradesh service area has the lowest Rural Tele-density of 41.76 followed by Bihar service area with rural tele-density of 43.15 in QE Sep-22. Despite improvements at the country level, there is a huge digital divide as compared to world level data ; even at regional level as reported by the UN-EGDI report of 2022.

INDIA IN GLOBAL COMPARISON

The United Nations E-Government Development Database (UNeGovDD) is a benchmarking tool that provides a comparative assessment of the e-government development of UN Member States. It offers an interactive snapshot of each country’s e-government development from a regional and global perspective. E-government has been

E-Government (2022 EGDI: 0.5883)	
2022 Rank	105
Group	HEGDI
Rating Class	H2
2020 Rank	100
Change	+5
E-Participation (2022 EPART: 0.5909)	
2022 Rank	61
2020 Rank	29
Change	+32

employed to mean everything from 'online government services' to 'exchange of information and services electronically with citizens, businesses, and other arms of government'. The E-Government Development Index presents the state of E-Government Development of the United Nations Member States. Along with an assessment of the website development patterns in a country, the E-Government Development index incorporates the access characteristics, such as the infrastructure and educational levels, to reflect how a country is using information technologies to promote access and inclusion of its

Source: <https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/en-us/Data-Center>

people. The EGDI is a composite measure of three important dimensions of e-government, namely: 1) provision of online services, 2) telecommunication connectivity and 3) human capacity. India ranked at 105 out of 193 countries.

EGDI:Telecommunications Infrastructure In

Index (TII)

Source: <https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/en-us/Data-Center>

Possessing an ICT device, having network access and knowing how to use the technology are necessary prerequisites to participate in the information economy. To understand this, a study was carried out by Indian council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER) surveyed the digital divide both in terms of ICT adoption (household's access to Internet enabled device(s) and Internet facility), and basic ICT use capabilities such as individual's ability to do word processing, search information from the Internet and use email. This study was based on the household survey conducted by National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) of GoI, on social consumption education during January-June, 2014 (71 st round). The findings were very clear that a) Respondents above the age of 14 years could

do word processing, search information from the Internet and knew how to email, **b)** Population with better income has better chances of adopting ICT, **c)** Education is also positively related to ICT adoption and its use capabilities, **d)** ICT adoption and its use capabilities varies across social and religious groups, **e)** urban area more likely to have ICT access **f)** At lower income levels the gap between rural and urban sector home ICT adoption is much lesser as compared to at the highest level of income in rural urban households.

LAYERS OF DIGITAL DIVIDE

It is vital to understand and address the ICT disparities at the household level in developing countries like India, as digital device(s) are not goods of individual possession rather goods of household belongings. Since digital device(s) are shared among the household members, the power structures of families in traditional households particularly those in the rural areas and lower income group households have a sharp negative skew against women, children, disabled and the elderly in both the access and adoption of ICTs.

India has one of the greatest **Gender gaps** in digital technology access in the world. According to the GSMA- The Mobile Gender Gap Report 2022, although roughly 50% of women possess a mobile phone, less than 22% use it for any other purpose than making a phone call and least of all any financial transactions. The gender gap in smartphone ownership is much wider than the gender gap in overall mobile ownership. India's digital gender gap is the result primarily of three factors. The first is a rural-urban divide, second is the income based divide and third is the Social

Norms, where women's online activities are governed by male relatives. Access to a mobile phone and mobile internet provides women with a range of opportunities to improve their lives, including with information and services related to income generation, education, health, finance, safety and personal well-being. India's gender digital divide is much more stark. The digital gender gap requires informed and targeted action from all stakeholders working together: mobile network operators, internet companies, policymakers and regulators.

Smartphone ownership in India, 2019–2021

Percentage of total adult population

Source: GSMA Consumer Surveys 2019, 2020 and 2021
 Base: Total population aged 18+
 n=966 to 1,099 for women and n=1,131 to 1,279 for men

There is a deep **Age related digital divide** between the Generations. A survey in the National Capital Region (NCR) found that 86% of senior citizens did not know how to use digital technology or computers. The data for other parts of the country will be similar and worse for rural areas, not to forget the gender dimension to this. This lack of knowledge may be attributed to a variety of factors, including lack of reliable internet access, cost of internet service subscription and devices, and the inability to read and write (literacy rates are very low among females of 65 years and above). Generally, aging is accompanied by a declining ability to understand, learn, and use cognition to adapt and use skills. Older persons are prone to losing their sensory abilities, which makes it more difficult for them to adapt to the ever-changing digital technologies. While these aging-related health challenges deter the use of digital tools, digital tools actually contribute to solving many of the challenges confronting seniors. Greater familiarity with digital tools may reduce dependency, increase autonomy and boost self-worth among India's fast-growing elderly population. Digital technology has to become more affordable, accessible and inclusive. The United Nations and UNESCO make recommendations for digital inclusion by direct action, primarily through local initiatives with a national scope, adopting a strategy of networked communities and informal learning.

The digital divide is widened due to **Linguistic and cultural differences**. More than 80% of content on the internet is in English and only 10% Indians are proficient in English. The people who are proficient in English are also more digitally adept. While India is a country with around 425 different languages and dialects, Hindi is the first language

of roughly 260 million people yet constitutes less than 0.1 per cent of all content on the web. The lack of content in local languages means that users' experience is highly impacted. The regional languages are completely unrepresented. With the launch of **Digital India BHASHINI (BHASHa INterface for India)** the internet experience will be democratized. This platform aims to collate the available technology to accelerate internet access, both in text and voice in local languages. This will be a vital stepping stone to onboard 500 million Indians onto the internet. This will reduce the digital gap among gender and generations too.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The digital divide in India both in the access and usage of ICTs and the internet is real and deep. It leads to an exclusionary consequence in the education, health and finance sectors. In a country plagued by high socioeconomic inequality, the digitisation process will take time particularly considering the existing human Capital indicators. The digital divide becomes particularly problematic when half of the population neither has access to gadgets and the internet or the technological know-how to move to a digital environment. In such circumstances, an unequal digitisation process may exacerbate the already existing inequalities. Greater efforts are needed towards digital inclusion by direct action, primarily through local initiatives with a national scope, adopting a strategy of networked communities and informal learning. There is a dire requirement of increasing the adoption and usage of ICTs among the less-favorable demographic profile (older age groups and women) and social groups of digital divide. The service providers should strategize and introduce technological solutions and innovative tariff plans to cater the price sensitive massive Indian market specially the underserved geographies. The Government of India has already launched several initiatives, programs and missions to reduce the digital divide which need to be implemented and well executed

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